

Variations in Calcaneus Articular Facets and Dimensions of Calcaneus: A Morphometric Analysis

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: To see the variations in articular facets and dimensions of calcaneus.

Material & Methods: A total of 120 dry calcaneus were procured from Department of Anatomy, Nalanda Medical College, Patna, Bihar, India.

Results: The most common type of articular facet on calcanei was type B. The width and length sulcus calcanei were: 5.28 ± 1.04 mm, 33.93 ± 3.33 mm respectively.

Conclusion: Analysis of morphometric parameters plays key role in reconstruction surgeries and foot rehabilitation procedures.

Keywords: morphometric analysis, calcaneus, articular facets

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Introduction

Articular facets of different types are formed on human tali and calcanei depending upon the gait and weight bearing habits [1]. Their relation is important in various orthopedic procedures and anthropometry [2]. These facets play a significant role in biokinetics of foot and ankle. The largest tarsal bone, calcaneus, and bear the daily stresses of weight-bearing owing to its design [3, 4].

Calcaneus is one of the key bones in deciding line of treatment in case of major injuries hence its morphometry and facet types need to be studied in detail.

The calcaneus has three superior and one anterior articulating surface. The talus articulates with all the three facets of calcaneum on superior surface. The calcaneal sulcus separates the anterior and middle facets from the facet found posteriorly. The sustentaculum tali support

the middle facet of the calcaneum. Both the middle facets of calcaneum and talus articulate with each other [5]. These facets vary with sex and race [6]. The anterior, middle and posterior subtalar facets function as a unit and any fracture disrupting their alignment leads to intra-articular fracture. The relationship between facets and its accurate 3-dimensional structural reformation is very important for proper functioning [7].

Classification given by Bunning & Barnett (1965) [8] was followed in the present study. Accordingly, three types type A, B and C. In Type-A consist of anterior and middle articular facets due to their extent of separation were again divided into four subtypes: A1 - distance between articular facets is less than 2mm, A2- distance between facets 2-5mm, A3- distance between facets more than 5mm. A4-only

one articular facet is seen. In type B – no separation between anterior and middle articular facets. Based on separation type B divided into two types. B1-separation incomplete, B2-no separation between facets. In type –C only one facet. Rarely, all three facets on the upper surface of the calcaneus fuse into a single irregular area. [9]

The main aim of present study is to know the incidences of variations in calcaneus articular facets and dimensions of calcaneus.

Material & Methods:

A total of 120 dry calcaneus were procured from Department of Anatomy, Nalanda Medical College, Patna, Bihar, India. All the bones were of unknown gender that are housed in the collection at department of Anatomy grossly normal without any physical damage. Types of articular facets on calcaneus were assessed by following the classification based on Bunning & Barnett (1963). To know the dimensions of (Table 1).

calcaneus bone Vernier callipers was used and parameters were recorded: antero-posterior length- it is the distance between the most anterior point on anterior surface and most posterior point on posterior surface, transverse width- the distance between most medial point on the medial surface and most lateral point on the lateral surface, while the width of the sulcus calcanei was taken as the distance between medial and lateral margins of the sulcus, while the length of the sulcus calcanei was taken as the distance between anterior and posterior margins of the sulcus.

The data was analyzed in M.S office and measured as mean and standard deviation.

Results:

Using the above classification, the following types of articular facet were observed on calcanei: A1- 1.66%, A7.5%, A3- 10%; A4- 2.05%. B1- 27.5%, B2- 50.83% and C -1.01% respectively (Table 1). The most common type of articular facet on calcanei was type B

Table 1: Number and % of articular facets of calcaneus

Types of articular facets	Number of bones	%
Type –A1 (less than 2mm)	2	1.66
A2 (2-5mm)	9	7.5
A3 (> 5mm)	12	10
A4 (only one facet)	3	2.5
B1(incomplete separation)	33	27.5
B2(no separation)	61	50.83
C (single facet)	0	-1.01

The anteroposterior length and transverse width of calcanei were: 75.88 ± 5.61 mm 42.71 ± 4.70 mm respectively. The width and length sulcus calcanei were: 5.28 ± 1.04 mm, 33.93 ± 3.33 mm respectively (Table 2).

Table 2: Mean and std of distance measured on calcaneus

Parameters (mm)	Mean±std
Anteroposterior length	75.88 ± 5.61
Transverse diameter	42.71 ± 4.70
Sulcus calcanei length	33.93 ± 3.33
Sulcus calcanei width	5.28 ± 1.04

Discussion:

The first constitutive features of the subtalar joint begin in the 8th week of gestation, with the talus and calcaneus being cartilaginous precursors. In the 11th week the cavitation process to form the subtalar joint develops differently in the anterior, middle and posterior regions. The embryology of the subtalar joint and formation of the articular facets on the calcaneus for the talus is extremely important for future joint function. [3] Racial differences are also present in developing fetuses, probably being genetically determined rather than resulting from other postnatal factors. Nevertheless, it is unlikely that the high occurrence of the separate type of facet is common in all populations. [10]

Morphometric measurements of calcaneus according to Uygur et al. (2009) were anteroposterior length and transverse width of calcanei were: 77.7 ± 5.65 mm 47.5 ± 4.2 mm respectively. The width and length sulcus calcanei were: 6.15 ± 2.7 mm, 30.4 ± 3.1 mm respectively, these findings are in line with the current study were anteroposterior length and transverse width of calcanei were: 76.01 ± 5.74 mm 45.94 ± 4.35 mm respectively. The width and length sulcus calcanei were: 5.63 ± 1.01 mm, 32.81 ± 3.78 mm respectively. [11]

Also, the measurements are influenced by heredity, race, lifestyle and environment. This observation is similar to the observations made by Mol et al., [12], Sarvaiya et al., [13], Chavan et al. [14]

It is appropriate to mention the accessory anterolateral talar facet which articulates with the calcaneus and which also has clinical implications. Aydingo'z et al. [15] in their MRI study found this variation was present in 32.7% of patients with ankle pain and in 26% of volunteers without it. Accessory anterolateral talar facet may contribute to painful talocalcaneal impingement in persons with pes planus. [16]

Conclusion:

Analysis of morphometric parameters plays key role in reconstruction surgeries and foot rehabilitation procedures

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